

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 9, No. 10; October 28, 2003

Dear Readers:

This issue is a typical non-special issue of J.UCS containing a delightful mix of papers, ranging from 'almost mathematics' to 'very applied': the first one on "Taxicab Numbers" starts out as an amusing paper on some number theoretic properties of integers and then shows how random computing techniques can help obtaining results that are true with "very high probability"! The second paper is a deep theoretical paper on patterns, the third, however quite topical, on testing wireless application protocols. Finally, the fourth and least theoretical one tries to explain why eLearning in schools has not lived up to its expectations, so far, and how this can be changed.

Enjoy!

Cheers,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
email: hmaurer@iicm.edu